

APQN Beyond First Decade of 21st Century

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In year 2000, World Education Forum was organized in Dakar. This was a milestone step towards Education for all. There had been a multivariate and multidimensional effort by all countries to align to their common goal of educating all. While much has been achieved over the past decade there is still lot to be done. Strategies aimed at equalizing opportunity in education have been formulated and the subsequent efforts have been clustered on the regional basis to accelerate the rate of growth in education sector. Broadly speaking education sector comprises of primary education, secondary and tertiary education with societal, economical and development aspect. This has led to the emergence of inclusive education. It is increasingly understood more broadly as a reform that supports and welcomes diversity amongst all learners – including boys and girls, students from ethnic and linguistic minorities, rural populations and provides learning opportunities for all youth and adults. Its aim is “to eliminate exclusion that is a consequence of negative attitudes and a lack of response to diversity in race, economic status, social class, ethnicity, language, religion, gender, sexual orientation and ability”. Education takes place both formally and non-formally, and within families and the wider community. Consequently, inclusive education is not a marginal issue but is central to the achievement of high quality education for all learners and the development of more inclusive societies.

It has been observed that societal development is directly linked to the GDP (GNP) of the country. Expenditure on education is very crucial part of GDP (GNP). If we look at the figures of public expenditure on education as the percentage part of the GNP, it varies very significantly from country to country - India among one of the lowest. If we look at the Asian and some pacific countries, it varies significantly. But the recent melt down has changed the earlier scenario and there has been drastic change in the strategy of countries.

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Education Sector after Economic Melt Down

According to the UNESCO's figure, by the end of the 2010 approximately 90 million people have been pushed towards extreme poverty. Moreover, the economies which are worst affected are not able to recover from high food prices and inflation. This has left another 175 million people malnourished. Education sector is also directly linked to poverty. Some countries have almost reduced the share of education in GDP, while some have drastically increased. The countries which pioneered in pulling out the world through this meltdown are China and India.

Almost all multinational companies are finding their base in either of these two countries or in any adjoining countries. The critical success factor now for these multinational countries is human capital. Earlier, United States or European Union countries were the centre of attraction of talent. This foundation has broken and thus the role of APQN (Asia Pacific Quality Network) has become very crucial. If APQN could fill that gap and produce high quality individual, then it could serve the purpose.

APQN (Asia Pacific Quality Network)

APQN was founded in January 2003 as a regional network in association with INQAHE to serve the needs of Quality Assurance Agencies across the region; the majority of which are from developing and growing economies. It started with a mission to enhance the quality of higher education in Asia and the Pacific region through strengthening the work of quality assurance agencies and extending the cooperation between them. The vision of the APQN was:

“To be a self-sustaining Network by 2010, in which it will come naturally to members to use APQN as a first point of reference for advice or support.”

APQN has broadly achieved the above-said vision, but there is need to formulate the strategy for future and that is why the theme of “What next for APQN”? Is the focus of this paper?

The countries in APQN have the following characteristic feature:

- They can be divided into four major regions based on their culture and quality of higher education

- Developed countries with high quality education system – Australia, New Zealand, Japan, Korea, Singapore
- Emerging and developing market with moderately good quality education system – India, China, West Asian countries (Kazakhstan)
- Poor countries like Bangladesh, Nepal, Bhutan
- Muslim countries – Iran, Brunei

- The quality of higher education in each sub-group is at the same platform.
- Each sub group is culturally similar
- Mobilization within sub groups is common, while inter group mobilization is rare
- APQN as a whole is not different from other regional networks
- The quality of higher education is dependent on many factors, like primary education, gender issues, poverty level,
- While practices differ, there is agreement on the essentials. Consequently, the various practices of quality assurance essentially fall under one of three basic approaches – Accreditation (yes/no certification of quality), Assessment (of the level of attainment in quality) and Academic Audit (of the processes that ensure quality).

In practice, some countries follow a combination of these approaches depending on their requirements. Whatever be their basic approach to quality assurance, the quality assurance frameworks of the Asia-Pacific region have five common critical core elements that are necessary to ensure the soundness of the quality assurance mechanism:

- i. Most of the quality assurance agencies are independent.
- ii. The assessment is based on pre-determined and transparent criteria.
- iii. The process is based on a combination of self-study and peer review.
- iv. There is public disclosure of the outcome (although the extent of public disclosure varies from disclosure of only the final outcome to disclosure of the full assessment report).
- v. The validity of the assessment outcome is for a specific period of time.

Many researchers opine that it is the quality of primary and secondary education that determines the quality of higher education. In the wide network of APQN, one very important aspect which is worth mentioning is that more than half of the population lives in extreme poverty. If we are trying to homogenize the quality of higher education, it would be unwise on our part to do it in isolation because higher education and primary education are complementary to each other. Different studies have shown a direct correlation between the net enrolment of primary, secondary and tertiary population. So, in my view if we are strategizing the policy of APQN for our future, it needs to be done in systematic way.

APQN – Future Strategy

The concept of boundaries is fading everyday. APQN should not limit itself to Asia and Pacific region but should try to include as many members as possible. As a first step, it should try to extend not only in Europe but also very aggressively in African countries. The social, political and economical structure of African countries may fit into any of our present four sub groups – Developed, Developing, Poor and Muslim countries. The APQN has good experience of handling all these together. APQN does not have to re-invent the wheel. It has its own strength and weakness as visible in SWOT analysis. As a first step we shall make SWOT Analysis of APQN as follows:

Strengths

- Wide Network
- Much ahead in the Learning curve
- Training and development
- Research orientation
- Effective management across nations
- Credit transfer schemes

Weakness

- Small and poor countries
- Lack of funds
- Dominant countries pushing their agendas
- Few enemy states
- Cultural divergence
- Apprehensions towards mobility of teachers

Opportunities

- “Torch Bearer” region for the world

- Huge investment to come into this region
- Africa to be the centre of action in years to come

Threats

- Vested interest of countries
- Vested interest of policy makers
- Other regional networks
- Relationship between INQAAHE and APQN

Step -2

In step 2, we club them based on their existing primary, secondary and tertiary education system (assumption here is that these are directly related to the level of poverty). One other important parameter that can be indicator of it would be the net enrolment at all levels, but the basic is primary education net enrolment rates and out of school. Owing to the similarity between African countries and some part of APQN, the model adapted in APQN region can be effectively replicated in our extended region

Step - 3

APQN need to understand and plan how the available fund and the experience can be diverted to the lowest or marginalized people. APQN need to form a resource pool of fund and human capital. Since everybody understand that one cannot grow in isolation; there has to be inclusive growth. To have the ‘balanced growth’ of the region there has to be flow of resources in both the directions- pool of APQN and other members (as shown in Symbiotic Model Fig.1). The

developed countries can be the source of fund while marginalized countries of human capital. The effectiveness of this “Symbiotic Model” depends on the quality of human capital.

The role of APQN becomes crucial at this juncture. There are many countries in APQN network which don’t have any established education system. So, bringing all at the same platform requires micro-planning at different levels. Once they reach that level the next level should be guided by the established system.

During each progressive step measuring standard should be different for different country, but the quality ranking need to be universal. Here, APQN also has to be in close connection with other similar regional bodies and also with the respective government bodies. The involvement of APQN during the policy formulation, especially related to education, need to be ensured so that it falls in line with APQN’s vision.

Challenges

The path to “education for all” is full of uneven terrains. The biggest hurdle is that the maximum member countries have their own vested interest. Countries, which would be donors, would try to impose their own terms and conditions. Secondly, financial support for programs will be a bottleneck. Thirdly, liaising with government to influence the education policy will be the point of concern. Moreover, when everybody is trying to expand their base, there will be conflict of interest.

Fig. 1: Symbiotic” Model

Conclusion

The global economic crisis has pushed quality education to youth to the centre of the 'Education for All' agenda. More broadly, there is recognition that, in an increasingly knowledge-based global economy, the premium on skills as a driver of employment, productivity and economic growth is rising. APQN, through its strong network in highly progressive area should try to expand its horizon to adjoining European countries and in African countries. The proposed Symbiotic Model could be implemented in the extended zone. The advantage of extending could serve many purposes; one getting the funds from its developed members and also in balancing the powers. Secondly, the much needed human capital for Multinational companies to expand their base in APQN region could be served. Though, task ahead is not easy, with lots of conflicts of interest and their own hidden agendas, APQN financial condition to launch many programs and achieving the goal can be achieved.

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